

METAL CHELATES OF $\alpha\beta$ -DIOXIMINOACETOACETAMIDES*

By J. S. DAVE AND A. M. TALATI

The dioximes, prepared from acetoacet(aryl) amides (where aryl amide may be anilide, *o*-toluidide, *o*-chloranilide, *p*-phenetidide or 2:4-xylylidide), have been used for the preparation of copper, nickel, cobalt, and palladium chelates. The magnetic susceptibilities of some of these chelates have been determined, and their structures suggested.

The metal chelates of α -dioximes have been studied by several workers (Tschugaeff, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1905, 46, 144; *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1907, ii, 75, 157; Pfeiffer *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1928, 61, 103; 1930, 63, 1811; Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 246; 1935, 621; Dwyer and Mellor, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 605; Banks and Haar, *ibid.*, 1955, 77, 324). In the present investigation, the formation of metal chelates by the dioximes derived from acetoacet(aryl)amides (where aryl amide may be anilide, *o*-toluidide, *o*-chloroanilide, *p*-phenetidide or 2:4-xylylidide) with copper, nickel, cobalt, and palladium has been studied and the magnetic susceptibilities of some of the metal chelates formed have been determined. It has been observed that these dioximes form brown paramagnetic chelates with copper, yellow, orange or red diamagnetic chelates with nickel, chocolate brown paramagnetic chelates with cobalt, and yellow or red diamagnetic chelates with palladium. Copper, nickel, and palladium chelates are formulated as $M(DH)_2$, where $M = Cu, Ni$ or Pd and DH_2 is a dioxime molecule, and cobalt chelates as $Co(DH)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$.

EXPERIMENTAL

The dioximes were prepared from the corresponding acetoacet(aryl)amides as mentioned earlier (*Curr. Sci.*, 1957, 26, 326). $\alpha\beta$ -Dioximinoacetoacet-*p*-phenetidide: m.p. 202-203°. (Found: N, 16.10. $C_{12}H_{15}O_4N_3$ requires N, 15.84%). $\alpha\beta$ -Dioximinoacetoacet-2:4-xylylidide: m.p. 194-95°. (Found: N, 17.0. $C_{12}H_{15}O_4N_3$ requires N, 16.86%).

Copper, Nickel and Palladium Chelates

The metal chelates were precipitated under specific conditions as mentioned below. These precipitates were digested on a water bath for about an hour, filtered, washed with water and ethanol, and dried at 110-20°.

(a). Copper chelates were obtained as brown precipitates on adding an ethanolic solution of the dioxime (0.011 *M*) to a warm, slightly acidified solution of copper chloride (0.005 *M*).

(b). Nickel chelates were obtained as yellow, orange or red precipitates on adding an ethanolic solution of the dioxime (0.011 *M*) to a warm, neutral solution of nickel chloride (0.005 *M*).

(c). Palladium chelates were precipitated as yellow or red precipitates on adding an ethanolic solution of the dioxime (0.0055 *M*) to a warm, fairly acidified solution of palladium chloride (0.0025 *M*).

Cobalt Chelates

Cobalt chelates were prepared by mixing an acidified solution of the cobalt chloride (0.005 *M*) with the ethanolic solution of the dioxime (0.011 *M*). On adding ammonium acetate to the mixed clear solution, chocolate brown precipitates appeared. The reacting solution was kept at room temperature for about an hour. The precipitates were filtered, washed with water and ethanol, and air-dried. The dried precipitates did not lose water on heating to 110-20°. The metal chelates, thus obtained, together with their colour, m.p. and analysis (micro) are recorded in Table I.

* Presented at the Symposium of Co-ordination Chemistry, Agra, Feb. 7, 1959.

TABLE I
Magnetic susceptibilities.

No.	Substance.		Colour.	M. P.	%Metal (micro).	
	M.	R.			Found.	Calc.
1.	Ni	phenyl	Orange-yellow	> 280°	11.61	11.76
2.	Ni	<i>o</i> -tolyl	Orange	..	11.13	11.13
3.	Ni	<i>o</i> -chlorophenyl	Orange-red	..	10.45	10.33
4.	Ni	<i>p</i> -ethoxyphenyl	Deep red	..	10.23	9.99
5.	Ni	2:4-xyllyl	Orange-red	..	10.20	10.57
6.	Cu	phenyl	Brown	235°	13.06	12.61
7.	Cu	<i>o</i> -tolyl	..	250°	11.92	11.94
8.	Cu	<i>o</i> -chlorophenyl	..	232°	11.34	11.09
9.	Cu	<i>p</i> -ethoxyphenyl	..	221°	10.47	10.73
10.	Cu	2:4-xyllyl	..	242°	11.86	11.34
11.	Pd	phenyl	Yellow	> 280°	19.55	19.50
12.	Pd	<i>o</i> -tolyl	..	..	18.40	18.55
13.	Pd	<i>p</i> -ethoxyphenyl	..	..	17.01	16.80
14.	Pd	2:4-xyllyl	Orange-red	..	18.23	17.69
Co(C ₄ H ₈ N ₂ O ₂ R) ₂ .ZH ₂ O:						
15.	Co	phenyl	Chocolate-brown	..	11.29	11.01
16.	Co	<i>o</i> -chlorophenyl	..	..	9.87	9.76
17.	Co	<i>p</i> -ethoxyphenyl	..	..	9.38	9.55
18.	Co	2:4-xyllyl	..	..	10.26	9.96

Magnetic susceptibilities of some of these chelates were determined using Gouy's magnetic balance. The field strength used was about 5×10^3 gauss. The results are recorded in Table II:

TABLE II

*Substance No.	$\chi_g \times 10^6$.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$.	T (Abs.).	μ_{eff} (B.M.).
1	-0.270	-134.7	..	304.0	Diamag.
2	-0.285	-150.2	..	308.0	..
5	-0.308	-171.0	..	304.5	..
6	+2.32	+1169	+1365	304.5	+1.83
7	+2.30	+1224	+1444	307.0	+1.89
11	-0.553	-302.5	..	305.0	Diamag.
13	-0.609	-386.7	..	308.0	o " o
15	+2.34	+1211	+1408	304.1	+1.85
18	+2.10	+1207	+1451	308.0	+1.50

* The number corresponds to those in Table I.

